

Growth of Life Insurance Corporation of India-An Overview

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Abstract

Life is like a bubble on water, because life is full of uncertainty and risks. Risk or uncertainty is the fundamental fact of life. It can be avoided taking precautions. Insurance provides strong hand & mind, protection against loss of property and adequate capital to produce more wealth. So insurance is a tool for transferring risk. This fund is used to cover any losses incurred by the insured in the event that an unpredictable event occurs. Life insurance is a business relationship built on trust and lasting for a long period of time between the customer and the insurance company. Insurance is the compensation amount against the risk and financial losses. There are many insurance companies such as public insurance companies and private insurance companies in India. The Life Insurance Corporation of India can play key role in the insurance industry. Throughout India's financial system the Insurance industry has played an important role. It has also helped India to achieve its goal of creating an efficient, effective and more stable economic environment. So I have selected the topic "Growth of LIC in Indian Life Insurance Industry". This is based on secondary data from IRDA, LIC annual report, other research paper and websites. The data are collected from the period 2018-19 to 2022-23 for analysis and also uses growth rates, percentage, average, tables and charts for comparison. The study found that LIC is improving their performance in terms of agents, investments, incomes, profit after tax, assets under management, market share, etc. So the study concludes that LIC increases their branches, launching new schemes and policies, adopting new marketing strategies for providing better services to customer. It also makes an advertisement to promote and aware about its insurance policies to the customers. LIC can provide better services to its policy holders and customers.

Key words: Insurance, Risk, PAT, Growth Rate, LIC, IRDAI

Introduction

Life is like a bubble on water, because life is full of uncertainty and risks. Risk can be avoided by taking precautions. So insurance is also one of the tool for protecting our life or business from the risk. Insurance can play an important role in financial system. It is not an investment instrument. It is the tool to transfer the risk. Insurance can protect business or human life from the financial losses which may occur due to unexpected events or uncertainties. The basic principle of insurance is that an entity will choose to spend small amounts of money against a huge unexpected loss.

Life insurance is a business relationship built on trust and lasting for a long period of time between customer and the insurance company. Throughout India's financial system the Insurance industry has played an important role. It has also helped India to achieve its goal of creating an efficient, effective and more stable economic environment.

Insurance is the legal contract between two persons (Insurer and Insured). Insurance is the cover for protecting the life of persons or businesses from the risk of financial losses. It is the compensation amount against the risk or financial losses. There are two parties involved in this agreement, i.e. Insurance policy holder and insurance company. The policy holder may be an individual or firms or businesses. So insurance is not investment tool, it is a tool to transfer of risk. Insurance can be classified in two forms. They are Life Insurance and General Insurance.

Life insurance can cover term life insurance, whole life insurance, health insurance, endowment life insurance, child plans for education, ULIP (Unit Linked Insurance Plans), pension plans etc., General insurance can cover fire insurance, marine insurance, health insurance, crop insurance, cattle insurance, vehicle insurance, travel insurance, home insurance etc.,

History of Life Insurance

The history of insurance is probably as old as the story of mankind. The same instinct that prompts modern businessmen today to secure themselves against risk, loss and disaster existed in primitive men also. They too sought to avert the evil consequences of fire and flood and loss of life and were willing to make some sort of sacrifice in order to achieve security.

Important Milestones in the Life Insurance in India

Year	Information
1818	The modern form of Life Insurance came to India from England. Oriental Life Insurance Company, the first life insurance company, was started by Europeans in Calcutta.
1870	Bombay Mutual Life Assurance Society was started, the first Indian Life Insurance Company.
1896	Bharat Insurance Company was started.
1912	Life Insurance Companies Act and Provident Fund Act were passed.
1938	Insurance Act was passed, the first legislation controlling Life and Non-Life Insurance.
1944	A bill to amend the Life Insurance Act 1938 was introduced in the legislative assembly.
1956	Life Insurance was nationalized in India with a capital of Rs. 5 crore.(Jan 19) Life Insurance Corporation Act was passed by the Indian Parliament.(June 19)
1956	Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) was established to expand life insurance, especially in rural areas.(Sep 1) LIC began with 5 zonal offices, 33 divisional offices, and 212 branch offices.
1969-70	LIC crossed Rs. 1,000 crore in new business.
1980	LIC crossed Rs. 2,000 crore in new business.
1972	General Insurance Businesses were nationalized by the General Insurance Business Act, effective from January 1, 1973.
2023	LIC operates with 2048 fully computerized branch offices, 113 divisional offices, 8 zonal offices, 1381 satellite offices, and a corporate office. LIC launched SATELLITE SAMPARK offices to provide easy access to policyholders.

Review of literature

- 1. Habeeb, M., Kote, A. K. B., and Nabi, T. (2016)** conducted a study to analyze how well the Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India is performing and how efficient its operations are. The research is based on data collected from LIC's annual reports, the Handbook on Indian Insurance Statistics (2014-15) published by IRDA, and other sources. The study highlights that LIC provides jobs to nearly one lakh people across India. However, men hold 83% of these jobs, while the percentage of women employed is significantly lower. The researchers emphasize the importance of reducing this gender gap to encourage more women to participate in the workforce. In terms of market share, the study notes that LIC's dominance has decreased. Between 2000-01 and 2009-10, its share of total premiums fell from 100% to 70%. To remain competitive and grow its business, the researchers recommend that LIC should introduce more life insurance policies. Additionally, they suggest that LIC adopt new marketing strategies and use advertisements to make people more aware of its insurance products. This would help the company retain its market share in a competitive environment.
- 2. Chandrapal, J. D. (2019)** conducted a study to evaluate how liberalization has affected the Indian life insurance industry, focusing on its overall performance by identifying key change factors and measuring their effects and interactions. The study found that liberalization had a positive impact on the industry, particularly in transforming the marketing mix, improving service quality assessment, and enhancing insurance education and awareness. These changes have contributed to the overall growth and development of the insurance sector. However, the study also revealed a gap between customers' expectations and the perceived quality of service. In addition, it showed that awareness about insurance was much lower in rural areas compared to semi-urban and urban regions. To address this, the researcher recommends that Indian life insurers develop innovative service delivery methods. In conclusion, while liberalization has positively influenced the Indian life insurance industry, significant challenges remain in providing world-class service quality and increasing insurance penetration and density across the country.
- 3. Prakruthi, M. V. (2020)** researcher aimed to understand how life insurance is important in people's lives, the benefits it offers to policyholders, and the growth of the

insurance industry in India. The study used a stratified sampling method and various statistical techniques to analyze the data. The findings highlighted that life insurance plays a vital role in reducing or eliminating risks related to life, property, and productive activities. However, the performance of the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) has declined due to tough competition from private insurance companies. To address this, the researcher suggested that LIC should introduce innovative policies that better serve policyholders' needs. Additionally, LIC should focus on creating schemes specifically for rural areas and recruit local agents to improve its performance and reach in these regions.

- 4. Lakshmanan, M. P. (2020)** conducted a study to explore the challenges and future opportunities for the life insurance industry in India. The study also examined how well life insurance companies have grown by analyzing certain key performance indicators. To understand the relationship between these factors, the researcher used a method called Two-Way ANOVA. The findings showed that the life insurance sector has experienced significant growth across various parameters. However, despite this progress, a large portion of the Indian population still does not have life insurance coverage. This presents a major opportunity for insurers to create innovative and customized products and improve their services to attract more customers. The study concludes that both the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) and private insurers must work harder to develop new products that suit the needs of the market and use creative ways to reach a wider audience across the country.
- 5. Kala, B. S. (2023)** conducted a study to compare the growth and performance of the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) with three private life insurance companies—HDFC, ICICI, and SBI. The research looked at various factors, including the number of branches, agents, policies, premium schedules, market share, total premium, claims paid, and share capital. The study used descriptive analysis and applied a multiple regression model. The findings showed that LIC earned a higher average profit compared to the three private companies. It also revealed that LIC had positive annual profit growth. Among the four companies, only ICICI achieved full technical efficiency, and this happened during the first five years of the study period (2010-11 to 2015-16). The study highlights that insurance companies can use this information to

understand their performance compared to competitors and take necessary steps to better use their resources.

The literature reviewed highlights the significant role of LIC in the Indian insurance industry and its performance amidst competition. However, most studies emphasize historical trends and generalized recommendations without a detailed assessment of recent growth trends, operational efficiency, and evolving strategies in response to market dynamics post-2018. Furthermore, there is limited exploration of how LIC's new initiatives, digital innovations, and rural outreach programs affect its overall performance and market share in the competitive environment. This study addresses these gaps by analyzing LIC's growth trends, policy performance, and strategies during 2018-2023.

Need of the Study

A life is full of uncertainties the insurance industry can play important role in human life. In this competitive environment LIC can improve their services to beat the private insurance companies. So the growth trend, performance of LIC and recent developments in LIC can provide clear picture about how the LIC can improve their performance and it also helps public to select insurance policies in Life Insurance Corporation of India.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze the growth trends and performance indicators of the Life Insurance Corporation of India.
2. To highlight the recent developments in life Insurance Corporation of India.
3. To identify areas of improvement and propose actionable recommendations for LIC to sustain its competitiveness in the Indian insurance market.

Research Methodology

The study was based on secondary data. The main sources of secondary data's were published LIC annual reports and IRDA report, books and research papers. In order to achieve the objective of the research a time series data on the relevant indicators have been collected during the period 2018-19 to 2022-23. The collected data were analyzed and presented in tabular form with the help of statistical tools such as growth rates, averages, percentage, Pie chart and table charts.

Data Analysis

New Business of LIC:

New business of LIC represents the expansions of LIC products portfolio to satisfy the consumer needs and preferences. It includes life insurance plans, pension schemes and investment linked pans.

New Business of LIC	
Year	No. of Policies (in Cr)
2018-19	2.07
2019-20	2.13
2020-21	2.10
2021-22	2.11
2022-23	1.96

The above table shows that the No. of policies of LIC in terms of crore. And the Pie chart shows that percentage of No. of policies from 2018-19 to 2022-23. The No. of policies are increasing year by year except 2022-23. But the percentage indicates that policies are decreasing comparing to previous year. i.e. 21%, 20%, 19%. It shows that the new business of LIC is not improving or not performing well. The average No. of polices of LIC is 2.074 p.a.

$$\text{Average} = \frac{\text{Total No. of Policies (10.37)}}{\text{No. of Years (5)}} = 2.074$$

Market Share of LIC (in terms of Policy):

The market share of LIC in terms of policies refers to the proportion of total life insurance policies sold in Indian market that are underwritten by LIC. It is calculated based on the number of individual or group insurance policies issued by LIC compared to the total number of policies sold by all life insurers in India.

Market Share of LIC	
Year	Market Share (in %)
2018-19	74.71
2019-20	75.90
2020-21	74.60
2021-22	76.60
2022-23	71.76

The above chart represents that market share of LIC in terms of policies. According to this the market share of LIC is decreases in 2022-23 comparing to 2018-19. But comparing to private insurance companies it acquires more than 70% of market share in India in terms of policies. So LIC can improve their services i.e. it can sold more & more policies to increase their market share in future days

Dividend Declared by LIC:

Dividend Declared	
Dividend (in %)	Dividend (in %)
380	380
400	400
425	425
425	425
425	425

The above table shows that the dividend declared by LIC in last 5 years i.e. 2018-19 to 2022-23. According to this table first 3 years dividend is increasing after that it is constant. The Pie chart shows that the percentage of dividend declared by LIC. Dividend means the share profit distributed to shareholders. The average growth rate of dividend declaration is 411% p.a.

$$\text{Average} = \frac{\text{Total Dividend (2055)}}{\text{No. of Years (5)}} = 411\%$$

Human Resources of LIC:

Total Human Resources	
Year	HR
2018-19	1,08,684
2019-20	1,14,498
2020-21	1,08,987
2021-22	1,04,036
2022-23	98,463

The above table represent the human resources of LIC from 2018-19 to 2022-23. Human resources includes class I officers, Development officers, class III & IV officers and Employees also. The above chart shows that No. of human resources are decreasing year by year except 2019-20. It indicates that the workers of LIC i.e. number of officers & employees are reducing from 2020-21 to 2022-23.

Assets Under Management (AUM):

An asset under management means the funds that LIC manages on behalf of policy holders and investors. AUM is a subset of the total assets. These assets are composed of investment made from premium collected from policy holders, such as Govt securities, corporate bonds, equities & other financial instruments.

Total Assets of LIC	
Year	Assets (in Cr)
2018-19	31,11,000
2019-20	34,14,000
2020-21	39,56,000
2021-22	43,59,000

2022-23	45,50,000
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The above table shows that Assets under management of LIC in terms of crore. The AUM is increases from 2018-19 to 2022-23. The growth in AUM represents LIC’s continued expansion and its ability to manage a substantial amount of policyholder funds through investment in various assets. Increases in AUM, the more substantial pool of investments LIC manages, which indicates its capacity to handle policyholder funds & generate return efficiently.

Total Investment of LIC:

Total Investment	
Year	Investment (in Cr)
2018-19	29,84,331.25
2019-20	30,69,941.67
2020-21	36,76,170.31
2021-22	40,84,826.84
2022-23	43,91,069.11

The total investment of LIC is represented in above table in terms of crore. According to this the investment of LIC is increasing yearly from 2018-19 to 2022-23. The pai chart shows that the percentage of investment of LIC in 5 years. Observing the pai chart we find that investments are raising in increasing order. The average investment of LIC is Rs.

36,41,267.836Cr p.a. It shows that the investment of LIC is increasing year by year from last 5 years.

Total Income of LIC:

Total Income	
Year	Income (in Cr)
2018-19	5,60,146.88
2019-20	6,14,718.85
2020-21	6,76,134.02
2021-22	7,21,215.99
2022-23	7,89,977.44

The above table represent total income of LIC from 2018-19 to 2022-23 in terms of crore. Total income of LIC is also increases from 2018-19 to 2022-23. The pai charthelps to find easily how much total income of LIC is increasing year by year in terms of percentage. Average increase in total income of LIC is 1.4% p.a. It shows that the performance of LIC is improving.

$$\text{Average} = \frac{\text{Total increase in Income (7\%)}}{\text{No. of Years (5)}} = 1.4\%$$

Total Assets of LIC:

The table represents that total assets of LIC. Total assets refers to the entire value of assets owned by LIC, including investments, real estate, cash, loans, receivables & other financial assets. It shows overall financial strength & resources of LIC.

Total Assets of LIC	
Year	Assets (in Cr)
2018-19	31,11,000
2019-20	34,14,000
2020-21	37,75,000
2021-22	42,30,000
2022-23	45,50,000

The chart shows that total assets of LIC is increases year by year comparing from 2018-19 to 2022-23. It represents the financial stability & capacity to pay out claims & other liabilities of LIC is improving in present years. It indicates that LIC is providing better services for its policyholders and investors also.

Policy Payment:

Policy payments of LIC include claims by maturity and claims by death.

Policy payment (in Cr)		
Year	Claims by Maturity	Claims by Death
2018-19	1,52,885.88	17,124.88
2019-20	1,52,601.78	17,552.70
2020-21	1,67,549.58	23,776.74
2021-22	2,09,068.50	36,205.64
2022-23	1,87,976.15	23,755.16

The above table and graph represents policy payments such as claims by maturity and claims by death. Considering the above 5 years claims by maturity and claims by death are increases from 2018-19 to 2021-22. After words in 2022-23 they are decreases. So LIC can concentrate on maturity claims and death claims. It increases the performance of LIC.

Profit After Tax (PAT):

The profit after tax of LIC represents the net income earned by the LIC after all expenses, including taxes, have been deducted from total revenue. It reflects the profitability and sustainability of LIC’s operations. It is an important factor for assessing the financial health & operational efficiency of the company.

Profit After Tax (PAT)	
Year	PAT (in cr)
2018-19	2,600
2019-20	2,800
2020-21	2,900
2021-22	4,000
2022-23	6,150

The above table represents the profit after tax of LIC from 2018-19 to 2022-23. It shows that PAT of LIC is increasing year by year. It represents how well LIC is managing its costs & generating revenue from its activities. It also represents LIC’s capacity to invest in growth & provide returns to shareholder. The significant change in profit for the year 2022-23 was primarily due to changes in accounting policies, specifically the transfer of funds from the non-participating account to the shareholders.

Recent development in LIC:

LIC launched LIC mobile app for agents, LIC call center services, agent recruitment apps are launched, work from home facility for employees are introduced by LIC. On 6th, March, 2020 online & paperless process of completion of Micro Insurance Policies launched. On 17th, May, 2022 LIC of India got listed on the Stock Exchange. LIC also launched LIC’s select interactive services for its customer and Policyholders on whatApp, etc.

Product Development:

LIC can offer variety of products and services, which fulfill the different needs of different customers of the society. During the financial year 2022-23 LIC introduced 7 new individual products such as LIC's BimsRatna, LIC's DhanSanchay, LIC's New Pension Plus, LIC's New Jeevan Amar, LIC's New Tech-Term, etc.

LIC also modified 5 individual products such as LIC's AadhaarShila, LIC's JeevanAkshay – VII, LIC's Saral Pension, etc. At the end of the financial year 2022-23 LIC had 37 Individual Products, 11 Group Products, 7 Individual Riders and 1 Group Rider available for sale.

LIC Premium Payment:

The Digital Marketing Channel started its operations w.e.f. 1st June 2021. LIC can provide various facilities for their clients. During the financial year 2022-23 this channel procured 12,696 online policies and Rs.75.48 crore first premium, 1,240 NPS funds business policies and Rs. 72.08 crore first premium and 2,775 PMVVY policies. For the financial year 2022-23 76.18% of the total premium payment transactions and 66.88% of the total renewal premium received by the LIC. It was collected through Alternative channels. Alternative channels are Electronic Payment Channels for Automated Debit, Online Premium Payment, Premium collection through Banks, Services on WhatsApp, Call Center Services, Customer Grievance Redressal, etc.

Focused Areas:

The Insurance Regulator has come up with a number of customer related activities such as Account aggregator, speedy grievance redressal via 'BhimaBharosa', proposed dematerialization of insurance policies and opening of distribution architecture, increasing the tie-up limits for Corporate Agents and Insurance Marketing Firms.

After COVID-19 most of the insurance companies have formulated various Risk Management Policies such as Risk Management Strategy, Crises Management, Business Continuity, Disaster Management and stricter Cyber Security Management Policies as a part of their Risk management process for better achievement of its goal.

New Business:

In the financial year 2022–23, 137.96 lakh people got insured for the first time. The total sum assured was Rs. 390877.86 crore. First-time insurance made up 67.53% of the total number of policies and 56.18% of the total sum assured for the year.

New insurance business from rural areas had a total sum assured of Rs. 116320.27 crore, covering 4544516 policies. This contributed 22.25% of the total number of policies and 16.72% of the total sum assured completed during 2022–23.

Findings:

1. LIC experienced growth initially it faced a slow decline in the later year (2022-23). It indicates a need for LIC to innovate or diversify further to meet evolving customer needs & market dynamics.
2. While LIC has maintained a strong lead in market share but it shows a downward trend in recent years. It indicates that other insurance providers are slowly gaining market.
3. Dividend has been shown a positive trend. It reflects that strong financial performance, and shareholder friendly approach.
4. The decline in human resources over recent years suggests LIC may be focusing on optimizing its workforce. It indicates strategic move toward modernization and efficiency.
5. The growth in AUM indicates strong assets accumulation capability, efficient management of premium and trust from policy holders.
6. The increase in total investment shows that LIC robust financial health, strong inflow from policyholders & effective management.
7. The increase in total income reflects LIC's effective business strategies, strong market position, etc.
8. The increases in total assets indicates that LIC has effectively managed its resources & investments, contribution
9. The policy payment shows that consistent growth in maturity claims, highlighting LIC's role in long term financial planning. And the temporary rise in death claims shows the impact of the pandemic, while the return to normal levels afterwards shows LIC's ability to handle changes in demand.

10. The increase in PAT for the company shows a strong and growing profitability trend, it represents company's improved efficiency & successful financial strategies,
11. The recent developments shows that LIC can launches many new schemes, provide variety of products, 24*7 customer service etc. and it also provide some online services for their customers such as digitized documents, online customer portal call centers etc.

Suggestions:

1. LIC could develop and promote products for younger & make them accessible through digital channels, focused effort to expand rural product offering can help grow market share.
2. LIC also diversify its investments and adopting more advanced risk management techniques for better return and support sustainable growth.
3. LIC should continue enhancing its online platforms and mobile apps, ensuring they are user friendly.
4. LIC could offer flexible working arrangements for specific roles to improve employee's satisfaction and attract diverse talent.
5. LIC could continue enhancing its profitability by analyzing cost structure focusing on digital tools to reduce operational expenses and balancing dividend growth with reinvestment can support long term profitability.
6. LIC also introduce more specialized products, affordable insurance products or micro-insurance plans targeting low income groups.
7. Increasing efforts in CSR, especially in areas such as health, education and financial literacy could improve LIC's brand image and help connect with consumers who care about social causes.
8. LIC should prioritize cyber security by investing in advanced security protocols to protect sensitive data and maintain customer trust.

Conclusion:

As per the study the LIC is performing in a competitive manner. The performance of LIC is improving in the year 2022-23 as compare to 2018-19, because the total investment, total income, number of agents, dividend declare by LIC are increases. The LIC introduce more and more new schemes and provide 24*7 online services for their customer. But the numbers of policies, human resources (No. of employees) are decreases. LIC also face many challenge

such as now a day's private insurance company provide more services and capture whole market. For this purpose LIC can launch new schemes, new policies, adopting new technology and marketing strategies, immediate solutions for customer problems, etc. and also LIC can provide better services to customers and policy holders. It also make advertisement to promote and aware about its insurance policies to the customer. Secured investment should be made by LIC to retain its reliable position with private sector insurance companies in the entire life insurance industry.

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